

2

Design Rationale of VR arena

Building a multimodal Virtual Reality arena for insects requires many considerations. Before one begins developing it for a new organism or system, one needs to consider many issues. This chapter is a first person account, catering to the obstacles one would encounter and key factors that should be considered before developing the project, such as the ability of the insect to fly on a tether, reliable optomotor responses, closing the loop and many small issues that can potentially derail a new project.

2.1 FLIGHT ON A TETHER

Understanding the behaviour of flying insects is challenging due to their size and speed. As mentioned in chapter 0, we are unable to track small flying insects in the wild and currently lack the ability to measure or manipulate their sensory cues. Flying insects search for their object of interest, such as host, prey or mate by integrating multiple sensory modalities. Although free flight VR arenas exist, dynamically measuring and manipulating their olfactory and airflow sensory environment is not possible even now. Therefore, a prerequisite for a multimodal VR is that these flies fly on the tether.

I tethered an apple fly (See chapter 3) to a tiny syringe needle using cyanoacrylate glue. Fortunately for us, this particular species was capable of flying for several minutes on a tether.* This is a major checkpoint for tethered VR, as many insects such as dragonflies and honeybees are known to not fly consistently on a tether despite being prolific fliers in the real world.

Figure 2.1: This is the image of the first apple fly, “flying” on a tether. One can even see the lack of precision due to the handheld tethering procedure.

2.2 OPTOMOTOR RESPONSES OF TETHERED FLIES

After confirming that the species of choice can fly for several minutes in succession on a tether, the basic prerequisite for VR is a behavioural response to stimuli while flying on a tether such as an optomotor response. In my case, to quickly establish if the fly was actively processing its visual scenery,

*To provide a landing and feeding surface, I gave a very tiny ball of tissue paper laced with a bit of sugar water.

I assembled a quick assay to test for optomotor head stabilization reflex using a toilet paper roll lined with the random pattern of black and white squares to provide visual contrast. I placed the tethered fly at the centre and quickly twisted the roll clockwise and anticlockwise by hand. I could see the fly rapidly turn its head right and left, trying to keep its visual panorama steady using saccades, confirming optomotor reflex in my system. [†]

2.3 DISPLAY CONSIDERATIONS

All visual systems have an internal sampling frequency at which they refresh their visual data. For example, under “standard conditions” of dimly lit environments with slow-moving objects, humans have a “sampling frequency” of about 12 hertz. Shannon-Nyquist sampling theorem ¹²⁴ dictates the sampling frequency to be at least twice the max detectable frequency. This is why most cinema projectors have a frame rate of at least 24 Hertz, a rate just high enough for the moving images to be perceived as a smooth motion like real life instead of a choppy slide show. This number varies wildly based on image content, brightness, amount of motion etc. A romcom or a family drama would look just fine to a human at 24 fps while an action movie on a large bright display will appear choppy to the viewer at 24fps. This discrepancy is primarily due to animal visual systems sampling asynchronously. Unlike in most modern cameras, where all pixel data is collected near-simultaneously, biological systems often operate independently of each other ³². So even though each photoreceptor has a “sampling frequency”, the ensemble of photoreceptors as a whole has a more nuanced behaviour and can’t be described with a few parameters. [‡]

[†]When pushed beyond a point, the fly not only uses its head but also adjusts its entire body stance. This range fractionation increases the dynamic range and speed of the stabilization.

[‡]The reader can test this herself by using a strobe app on a mobile phone. To measure your “flicker fusion frequency”, increase the strobe frequency until you no longer see any blinking. Without changing anything, now shake your head rapidly or wave the phone swiftly, whichever is easier. You’ll now easily be able to see the light blink! By adding a spatial as well as temporal feature, one effectively increases the perceptual “flicker fusion frequency”.

Insects have completely different visual systems and evolutionary history when compared with humans. Their optics, phototransduction systems and ecological necessities have resulted in much higher sampling frequencies than humans, often over 150Hz. However, most consumer computer monitors have a refresh rate much lower than of insect's sampling frequency.

Cathode Ray Tube (CRT) and Plasma displays have excellent refresh rate and contrast ratio. They also enable arbitrary stimuli generation. However, they suffer from ghosting and flickering making it unsuitable for our use case of object tracking.

Projectors have great refresh rate, but due to the spinning discs that are inherent to their design, make the colors ghost rapidly creating severe artefacts. By removing the wheel, one can get an excellent monochrome display and have been successfully used in insect VR⁸². Custom built LED panels⁸¹ address the previous challenges of artefacts and refresh rates and makes it suitable for insect vision. However, making arbitrarily complex, colorful visual scenes isn't possible yet and therefore wasn't an option for my study. Due to the limitation of available technology and logistical delays, which was a major factor in all my design choices, I initially attempted to use commercially available technology. I placed my target species, the apple fly, in front of a monitor which had a similar random black and white checkerboard pattern image displayed on it. Using the mouse, I panned

Figure 2.2: The fly is placed in the centre of a toilet paper roll, lined with a random checkerboard pattern. By rotating the cylinder by hand, one can elicit optomotor responses from the fly. To stop the fly from flying and tiring itself out, I gave a very tiny ball of tissue paper laced with a bit of sugar water. The fly holds on to this as a steady platform and a source of nutrition.

Figure 2.3: The fly is placed in the centre of two LCD monitors. The gratings displayed on the monitor provide yaw stimuli by moving back and forth from left to right at different velocities. The fly exhibits the classic signs of optomotor responses by following the stimuli and keeping its visual panorama steady.

the image left and right similar to the toilet paper test. The flies responded with an appropriate saccading optomotor response. This was surprising to us, as traditional insect virtual reality arenas either use a physical drum, lined with different visual patterns or use custom-built very high refresh rate LED panels. And, insects are known to respond to flickering artefacts of human-based displays. However, in many of these previous VRs, a major purpose was to assess visual processing, where such flickering artefacts would introduce noise into subsequent neurological recordings and assessments, making LED panels the only possible option. As I was mainly interested in object detection, subsequent experiments described in chapter 3 indicated that these artefacts did not impact virtual object tracking. Another key factor for the decision to use off-the-shelf gaming monitors was the added ability to provide complex colourful naturalistic stimuli in three dimensions relatively easily.

2.4 CLOSING THE LOOP

Once behavioural response to VR stimuli is validated, one needs to feed the behavioural output of the organism back into the system to close the loop. This enables the organism to control the synthetic stimuli while also providing the opportunity for experimental manipulation. This is what distinguishes VR from other immobilized assays. There are many ways to achieve this task and some of the common methods are discussed below.

2.4.1 TORQUE COMPENSATORS

Initially, virtual reality arenas used a torque compensator⁷⁶ to measure the organism's motor output as a proxy for the behavioural response. This was an intricate piece of electromechanical equipment that measured the torque by compensating a proportional current in the system. Despite its power, it's a challenging piece of equipment to build even today. (Figure 2.4 on page 25)

2.4.2 OPTICAL WING BEAT ANALYSER

Later in 1986¹⁰⁸, Gotz and colleagues built the optical wing beat analyser. This closed the loop by illuminating the fly's wings and measuring the corresponding wing shadow on a piece of a silicon wafer. The wafer was masked by a hand-drawn stencil, which increased the sensitivity and dynamic range of the subtle differences in the shadow. Back in 2015, when I started building my VR, shadow-based optical wing tracking was the norm. However, most research articles then cited the original publication for the detailed description of materials and methods. The challenge, however, was that the technology and equipment from 1986 are quite different than what is available now; such as obtaining a large piece of silicon wafer.

Upon further investigation, it became apparent that the reason silicon wafers were used was that they were the most light-sensitive materials available in those days. But in the recent era of digital

Abb. 3. Das Doppelspulen-System

Figure 2.4: Peter Kunze and colleagues built one of the first Virtual Reality arenas for insects. From⁷⁶

electronics and LED, we have light-sensitive arrays of tens of millions of pixels packed within a small space - an LED and photodiode are as sensitive as a silicon wafer from a half-century ago. So I built a small circuit consisting of a photodiode and LED and connected it to an oscilloscope.[§] The degree of occlusion affects the amount of IR light that falls on the photodiode and is quantified by the voltage across it. By placing a tethered fly in the path of this light beam, one could see the oscillations on the oscilloscope due to the cyclical occlusion of the light beam. By positioning the fly carefully, one could see the double peaks produced by the wingbeats.

However precise positioning is non-trivial and also requires considerable custom electronics to be built.[¶] In search of simple ways to close the loop, I stumbled upon an acoustic method to detect wing beat difference. The frequency and amplitude are straightforward to measure with sound. But localized sound amplitude differences are tricky as the position of the microphones must be precise and balanced on both sides¹²⁵.^{||}

2.4.3 CAMERA BASED WING BEAT ANALYSER

To address this issue, camera-based tracking approaches to close the loop were developed¹⁰⁹. Since this is a camera based approach, it reduces the complexity of the setup and makes tuning easy. It also reduces the cost of the setup as it requires no custom electronics for data acquisition as all processing is software-based. The wing beat amplitude difference is measured by detecting the amount of wing beat blur on each side. This requires one to sample no higher than wing beat frequency to capture a full wing cycle and prevent aliasing artefacts. This gives an average cycle to cycle torque difference instead of the instantaneous torque from the compensator. But for most research questions, this is

[§]This simple circuit worked like the numerous photosensitive IR couples around us, from our mobile phone proximity sensors to the elevator doors.

[¶]To make sure the fly is positioned correctly in the light path, one has to ensure the light is exactly focusing and falling on just one wing. Also, adding the mask on the tiny LED is not straightforward.

^{||}One has to isolate the left and right-wing sound amplitudes carefully enough to pick up the subtle differences between them.

not a big impediment, as even torque signals themselves were often downsampled to roughly 200 Hz¹⁰⁸. However, It is unsuitable for many groups of insects that have a lower wingbeat frequency (See Figure 3.14 on page 59).

2.5 PILOT VR ARENA

To test if my chosen species could control virtual reality in closed-loop, I used simple bar gratings as the visual stimuli. This is a well-established assay in the VR paradigm and makes it convenient to check if the system is responding properly. Using Psychopy Toolbox¹²⁶, I generated the grating on the monitor with constant drift and its horizontal position was controlled by the insect's wing beat amplitude difference. The moment the closed-loop was enabled, the constant drift of the grating stopped and instead started to oscillate about an arbitrary setpoint; a classic optomotor stabilization response. I moved the stripe world clockwise and anticlockwise at different speeds and the apple fly kept them stable, establishing the system was responding effectively and my insects could control the VR.

Next, I made an extremely simple world using a flat terrain with a grass texture amidst a blue sky with clouds. In this flat earth, I added a simple green sphere as an object. I placed the fly in this virtual world and it could freely orient in the world in any direction it chose but in my initial experiments, the insects oriented towards the green sphere. I also provided constant forward velocity to the fly at the same virtual ground speed as that recorded in this species in flight tunnel assays (approximately 1 m/sec CE Linn, Jr., pers. comm.) I “reset” the fly back to its initial position and it oriented to the sphere again. This was a promising advance in terms of foreground segmentation and navigation to virtual objects.

To probe further, I placed two identical virtual spheres on either side and let the fly orient freely. The fly oriented straight ahead between the spheres initially and then oriented randomly to one

of the spheres and approached it via the forward velocity given. When I repeated this experiment, the apple flies approached either sphere at a 50:50 ratio. This established a simple choice assay to assess insect behaviour in virtual reality. I then created a 3D apple tree as these insects are known to approach ripe apples in the tree in nature. When I tested it with a fly, the fly oriented towards and approached the tree directly. These pilot results established that my pilot virtual reality pipelines could be used to study insect search behaviour, and were repeated with other insects and virtual objects to assess the robustness of the arena for different species (see Chapter 4).

2.6 STIMULI CONSIDERATIONS

To understand navigation and multimodal search behaviour in complex environments, one needs to move beyond two-dimensional stimuli such as bars and stochastic pattern. In the real world, depth cues are indicated to the observer in that closer objects move faster than farther ones, objects expand as they get closer, and objects in the direction opposite of the motion contract. One could in principle capture all these aspects using simple stimuli such as dots and many classic screensavers employed this trick. This technique was also how much of our understanding of insect vision was established^{61,62}.

However, modifying tiny dots individually to simulate 3D is rather challenging. Historically, this was the only way to reconstruct 3D with limited computation power. Also, technological considerations from drums and LED panels made the arbitrary motion unfeasible. I chose against stripes and dots as visual stimuli as I was keen on understanding decision making in naturalistic contexts. Current display technology also enabled the use of photorealistic visual stimuli with contrast, textures, occlusion, heterogeneous lighting and other features. By making use of the advances in game development engines such as Unity¹²⁷, providing a 3D world is easier than coding individual dots and stripes to mimic the real world.

Figure 2.5: The pilot VR arena used 2 LCD monitors to provide visual stimuli to the flies. The servo motor with a suction pipe provided the necessary airflow cues. The flies were illuminated by white LED's which caused distracting glares. The dissection microscope on the top was hooked with a camera for wing tracking and closing the loop. The monitors are rendering a weeping willow from Hogwarts.

Despite the behaviour evoked in my pilot arena, it was quite limited in many aspects. It had an extremely slow refresh rate of 60 Hz and since they were old monitors with older display technologies internally, it had a sluggish LCD update system. The displays subtended a horizontal field of view of 180° and a vertical field of view of roughly 60°. This thus covered only $\frac{1}{6}$ of the complete solid angle which severely limited the widefield cues I could provide to the fly. Also, the monitor orientation presented a constant central black stripe due to the bezel of the two monitors and a very dim backlight of 50 Lux.

Due to these restrictions, I developed a new setup that provided 360° visual input with the highest refresh rate possible. I used an In Plane Switching (IPS) panel for wide-angle viewing with the brightest backlit possible while having minimal bezels and a matte finish. I used gaming monitors and the monitor that met all these criteria at the time of arena development was Asus ROG

Figure 2.6: To make identical tethers, I built a jig that could make identical yet customizable tethers by hand.

PG279q. Additionally, the monitor had a built-in stand for portrait viewing. This made the arena cover an even larger fraction of the visual field in the elevation axis.

2.7 TETHERING AUTOMATION

To provide perspective accurate stimuli, it is necessary to position the fly at the exact centroid of the triangle prism made by the three monitors. However, there is huge variability in the final position of the insect due to variability in the handmade tethers. Although there is a 3D micromanipulator for fine adjustment, due to bursty intermittent flight bouts of most flies, finely adjusting the position for each fly is inconvenient. As more often than not, by the time one finishes adjusting for the given fly, it no longer chooses to fly.

To address this, I had to make all the tethers as identical as possible. One option was to CNC machine them but it had a long lead time from idea to end result. So I established a simple setup using 2020 aluminium profiles. Using screws and rubber bands for the fine adjustment of tether size, and a sliding head with a snapping magnet. This jig allows one to make identical tethers by hand while

Figure 2.7: The tether jig enabled rapid prototyping of new tether designs and dramatically increased experimental efficiency by enabling hot swapping of insects in VR from the army of tethered flies.

also being customisable for different sized tethers for varied insects. This enables rapid prototyping of new design and dramatically increases experimental efficiency by enabling hot swapping of insects in VR.

2.8 DESIGNING A CLOSED LOOP WINDSCAPE

The long-range search behaviour of apple flies towards apple trees is inherently multimodal. It is well known that they make use of vision, olfactory and airflow cues for plume following^{13,128,68}. So my goal was to be able to dynamically alter the wind direction in closed loop. To provide airflow input to the fly, I attached a suction pipe on a servo arm. The suction was provided by a centrifugal fan. The servo can only turn 180° and by placing the suction pipe at the rear end of the fly, I could effectively simulate upwind and crosswind configurations. However, this setup created a variety of issues I outline below that eventually led to my current design described in Chapter 3.

2.8.1 STUCK IN A SERVO SPIRAL

The windscape measures the difference between the virtual heading angle of the flight and the wind angle of the windscape at the flies' current virtual location. When the difference is 0°, the fly is downwind, at 180° is exactly upwind and 90/270° are exactly crosswind. Due to the mechanical limitations of my initial servo motors, I could not simulate exact downwind conditions. This was reasonable as I expected them to fly upwind to follow the plume. But due to the limitation of my mechanical setup, when the flies tried to fly downwind, I not only provided inaccurate feedback of being crosswind as the servo Motor is stuck at either 90° or 270° position; but also created a spiky artefact as the servo has to rapidly do a 180° turn to be on the other end. This rapid acceleration is not only challenging for the servo electronics but this sudden movement also caused a clear optic flow signal, strong enough for the fly to respond. Once the flies detected this, they exhibited a rapid

Figure 2.8: The new VR with the servo motor to provide airflow cues. The capillary in the front provided odour cues. Due to the contrast between the moving parts and the sky in the background, the flies responded to the movement of the servo and oriented in a spiral pattern, trying to evade the servo motor itself.

counter turn. This rapid counter turn often induces the servo to rapidly turn 180° to the other side and this vicious feedback loop repeats itself.

To check if this erratic behaviour was visually mediated I disabled the airflow and tested it again while keeping the monitors turned on and they continued to go in circles. I turned off all the monitors and made a completely dark environment and tested again in the presence of wind and this did not cause any erratic behaviour. This conclusively showed that the visual cues of the moving servo were the reason for the erratic behaviour and not any spurious vibration or mechanical cues.

2.8.2 HIDING BEHIND A VEIL

After many failed attempts at making the servo arm transparent using glass parts, 3D printing PETG and CNC machining acrylic, I created a cylindrical veil behind the fly. This allowed the air to pass freely but occluded the moving suction arm behind it. I 3D printed cylindrical meshes of varying grid sizes. Despite all these optimisations and trials with various mesh sizes, the flies would still orient in loops whenever the servo moved. This was because the background of the servo arm was the bright sky being rendered on the monitors and the silhouette of the servo arm still had enough contrast through the mesh

2.8.3 TRYING TO MAKE THINGS INVISIBLE

To make the servo invisible, instead of making it transparent, I tried to minimise contrast. I covered the entire servo arm with pitch-black velvet to remove all reflections. Then I used a patch of the same velvet on the monitors to further minimise background contrast. Even after all this, the flies responded to the visual motion of the servo. On closer examination, I realised that velvet is fantastic at cutting all reflections and absorbing all the incident light on it. But the fabric is still quite transmissive when placed on a very bright monitor, as some light still bled through the velvet cloth. That transmitted light gave enough background contrast to the flies. To attempt to resolve this issue, I

Figure 2.9: All the moving parts were occluded by the 3D printed veil while letting the air pass unobstructed. I hoped this would reduce the servo spirals, but it did not.

virtually rendered a black rectangle in the rear field view, where the velvet patch was pasted on the monitors. This made the servo covered in black velvet, in a background of the same black velvet material, seen through a black veil. However, the flies still responded to the servo movement. After searching extensively, I learnt about fresnel reflection¹²⁹ at oblique angles.** When the velvet is wrapped around the arm, there will always exist at least one point on the surface which is oblique with respect to the fly and the monitor and acts as a mirror, creating a bright spot on a dark background. This behaviour itself could be examined in future studies. However, these limitations are what drove us to my current design of “Rasen shuriken”.(Figure 3.8 on page 50)

2.9 CONCLUSION

Devising an apparatus to fool an organism is not as easy task. A successful VR requires multiple things to be just right simultaneously, resulting in a challenging debugging process as there are far too many reasons for it to not work. To simplify this process, these are the considerations I would keep in mind. Ensure that your model organism flies/walks/swims in your constrained laboratory conditions of tethering/treadmill/pool. Once the animal behaves under restraint, the next step would be to devise the virtual sensory systems. Depending on the choice of the model organism, careful consideration should be given to match the sensory resolution and ecological relevance of the virtual cues with the real world, whilst minimizing latency and technical artifacts. I would follow this up by verifying if the organism is responding to virtual sensory cues as expected from the real world. Optomotor responses, c-start or other relevant reflexive behaviours are a great to choice to validate proper sensory processing to virtual input under constrained conditions. Once these open loop tests are established reliably, it is time to close the loop. Depending on the system, it could be wing beat amplitude difference, number of steps taken or amount of tail whip. This would then

**This is the same thing that makes even black granite behave like mirrors at oblique angles and also give you shiny spots on your nose and cheek despite applying matte makeup.

be followed by calibration and characterization of closed loop feedback ensuring the organism has access to as much of its natural range of motions, both in terms of degree and kind.

Building a VR arena demands one to be cognizant of the tiniest details while having the larger purpose of the study in mind, from the amount of glue used to tether them to the ecological context of the behaviour under study. By actively trying to put ourselves in the tiny minds of our model organisms, we often realize our folly of what we thought would've been significant isn't actually. And what we thought is a minor detail often means a great deal to the organism. This approach is anthropomorphic and is certainly biased, but one is always biased towards a point of view, wittingly or unwittingly. Since our goal most often is to understand the organism, studying with its ecological context is an excellent guiding principle. The phrase often repeated by my advisor and my advisor's advisor, aptly summarizes what matters and what doesn't in designing an experiment. *Think like a fly.*

Figure 2.10: I covered all the parts with matte black velvet, including the background, with a black patch rendered on the monitor to prevent light bleed. Despite all this and being behind the veil, the fly continued to orient in spirals.

Figure 2.11: The Rasen shuriken went through many iterations, these were its humble beginnings.